

INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH.

Egamberdiyeva Iroda

senior teacher of ASIFL.

Abduraximova Moxirabonu

Odiliva Iroda

Faculty of english language and literature

Department of tour guiding, intercultural communication and translation studies.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7858539>

Annotation: This article provide information about interactive learning - a modern way of learning, which consists in the interaction of all participants in the educational process: teachers and students. Today we should talk about the use of interactive methods of training, which encourage interest in the profession; promote the efficient acquisition of training material; form patterns of conduct; provide high motivation, strength, knowledge, team spirit and freedom of expression; and most importantly, contribute to the complex competences of future specialists.

Key words: interactive methods, think-pare-share, stem, bloom`s taxonomy, discussions, debates, group works.

Interactive learning is associated with many benefits for students. Group work that is a common element of interactive learning more closely aligns with the collaborative methods of most occupations and professional academics. Research consistently finds that interactive methods correlate with positive student outcomes, such as higher rates of attention, interest in subject matter, and satisfaction. Interactive classrooms also perform better on measures of student learning. One meta-analysis found that in STEM classrooms with “active learning,” broadly defined, student exam scores improved by about six percent. In addition to greater retention, interactive classrooms perform better on higher-order learning measures of Bloom’s Taxonomy, like analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. Furthermore, interactive learning is associated with improved learning for typically at-risk students, like minorities and first-generation college students, making it an important part of inclusive teaching. Students may initially resist interactive learning methods. Lack of experience with interactive learning, the greater effort that is required of students in interactive learning, and the impression that the instructor is abdicating the “teacher” role can factor into students’ resistance. Therefore, it is important for instructors to explain the reasons for interactive learning in general. Instructors should also explain the specific reasons for each particular interactive learning exercise, provided they have carefully selected methods that are appropriate to learning goals and

students' abilities. The possible methods for interactive learning are perhaps limitless, constrained only by creativity and resources. Below are some of the most common interactive learning strategies, organized from least intensive to most intensive, compared to traditional lectures.

Conversational technology is often contrasted with a lecture-only audience, but lectures can be powerful interactive experiences. Anyone who has shared a TED Talk knows this. Learning occurs when teachers carefully connect new material to students' prior knowledge and important human experiences, and when teachers use narrative structures to intentionally stimulate students' interest and imagination (create conflict or tension and then make decisions). Such methods should not be for entertainment, but really stem from questions or problems inherent in the subject. Teachers can easily add an intentional, interactive element to their classes by interrupting and encouraging students to ask clarifying questions.

Some interactive methods require less time to prepare and implement. Short writing exercises, along with formative assessments, help students review, understand, and think critically about the material. These exercises can target different levels of thinking. For example, asking students to list items from previous lectures reinforces background knowledge. Asking students to repeat central concepts in their own words promotes understanding. By asking students to use information to solve new situations, students practice using it.

Another simple interactive method is Think-Pair-Share. The teacher presents a problem or question and first asks students to provide their own answers along with evidence and arguments. Students then discuss the answers with their partners, and the teacher encourages polite questions and criticism among students. Finally, students share their knowledge (from individual and pair discussions) with the whole class, prompting further questions and criticism. Argument

Think-Pair-Share can be seen as a combination of short writing and discussion. Interactive classroom discussions can be used in a number of ways. Students discuss in pairs, in small groups, or with the whole class at once. Similarly, a discussion can be a short interlude or the entire agenda of a class session. Depending on the pedagogical objectives, the teacher can involve himself to some extent in real-life conversations. However, as a form of interactive learning, discussion should strive for the free exchange of ideas, and arguments should be constructed and critiqued through logic and evidence.

Debate. Like discussions, discussions are designed to encourage students to share their thoughts and challenge each other's ideas. Discussions can be especially helpful when teachers want to understand and appreciate perspectives that students may not have. Rather than often consensus-seeking discussions, discussions are competitive in nature and tend to obscure the similarities of opposing viewpoints. Teachers should recognize that discussions foster an adversarial mindset and convey the impression that complex issues are binary. One way to facilitate this is through "panel" discussions to better understand the complexities and nuances. problematic education

Problem-based learning is a challenging yet effective interactive strategy for students and teachers. Many other strategies begin by presenting the material and then ask students to apply their individual knowledge to a well-defined problem or question. Problem-based learning, however, begins with an open-ended, usually realistic (ie, "real-world") problem in which students (often in groups) are asked to decide what they know and need to know to solve. problem. Solve a problem, decide how to obtain the necessary knowledge, formulate a hypothesis/research/ experiment, determine a solution, and report the results. Based on the theory that open-ended inquiry increases student motivation, the obvious advantage of this approach is that the acquired knowledge appears immediately in a meaningful context.

Used literatures:

1. Bonwell, C., & Eison, J. A. (1991). Active learning: Creating excitement in the classroom. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Reports.
2. Felder, R. (2007). Sermons for grumpy campers. Chemical Engineering Education, 41(3), 183-184. \
3. Абдурахманова, С. Е. (2016). Современные транспортные магистрали Великого шелкового пути в Евразии. Молодой ученый, (3), 723-726.
4. Кучкоров, У. И., Хамроев, С., & Илёсов, Б. У. (2022). Дифференцированная Терапия И Тактика Лечения Когнитивных Расстройств При Разных Формах Шизофрении. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 3(11), 258-264.
5. Хамроев, С. Б. (2023). ШИЗОФРЕНИЯ КАСАЛЛИГИДА КОГНИТИВ ФАОЛИЯТ БУЗИЛИШЛАРИНИ НАМОЁН БЎЛИШИНИНГ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI, 3(4), 72-80.

6. Khamroev, S. B. (2023). Characteristics of Cognitive Impairment in Schizophrenia. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(4), 61-70.
7. Khamroev, S. B. (2022). Differentiated Therapy of Cognitive Disorders in Schizophrenia Taking into Account the Dynamics of Clinical and Sociological Parameters. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 1(5), 127-131.
8. Содикова, А. Х. (2023). ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ СТУДЕНТОВ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(5), 118-124.
9. Содикова, А. Х. (2019). Признаки процесса обучения. *УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА*, 49.
10. Erkin, E., Jamila, S., & Dilmurod, M. (2022). SCHIZOPHYLLUM COMMUNASI FR. ON THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN ISOLATION OF PURE CULTURE OF MEDICINAL FUNGUS. *Universum: химия и биология*, (6-4 (96)), 4-7.
11. Sherkulova, J. P., Mustafaev, I. M., Sharopova, M. A., Chariev, R. R., & Eshonkulov, E. Y. (2020). Micromycetes Of Class Leotiomycetes Distributed On Ornamental Trees Introduced In The Conditions Of The Southern Part Of Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(03), 2020.
12. Erkin, E., Dilmurod, M., & Navbakhor, K. (2022). MEDICINAL SCHIZOPHYLLUM COMMUNA FR. THE FIRST REPORT OF THE FUNGUS WHICH IS DISTRIBUTED IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN. *Universum: химия и биология*, (11-3 (101)), 13-16.
13. Sh, N. G., Salimova, D. E., & Alisherovich, B. A. (2022). RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY AND CARDIAC DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES. *PEDAGOG*, 1(2), 337-340.

